

(NCF) ----- National Curriculum Framework 2005

Dr. Saroj Kumawat

Assistant Professor

Prince College - Sikar

Introduction: The chairman of this committee, Prof. Mr. Yashpal was there.

Aadhar: Teachings of 1993. Leave the person free without burden.

Essay: The essay titled Civilization and Progress is written by Rabindranath Tagore.

Statement: The creative bountiful joys of early childhood are the key. It is threatened by unwise adults.

Scholars: There were 38 scholars in this.

Sutra: Sutra of National Curriculum Framework - Learning without burden.

Its goal is to create self-knowledge.

Chapter - In this structure mainly chapter which is written in 180 pages.

1. Perspective - Education to Change the Curriculum of Freedom.
2. Learning - Importance of Interaction. Mediation of direct. Best Method.
3. Curriculum - All subjects covered (objective language).
4. School and classroom environment - Information Technology. Role of Library.
5. Systematic - Examination System, Assessment System, Development in Children.

Curriculum-

The English word "curriculum" is derived from the Latin word currere (the racetrack - where we run to reach the goal).

According to Munro - All the experiences are included which the school does nine yoga. Done to achieve the objectives of education.

According to Froebel - The essence of human experience.

According to Cunningham - The curriculum artist is the instrument in the hands of every teacher, by which he molds the student according to his orders.

1. According to the aim of education, the child can understand the meaning of life.
2. Value - Which promotes a society with peace, humanity and cultural diversity (religion caste but all remain one).
3. Children are only receivers of knowledge. The basis of this text book examination changes this assumption.
4. Mechanical learning takes away the happiness of the child.
5. Background - The National Education Policy 1986 talks about a common center of the national curriculum, which can be molded according to the local environment. After this - 2005 also does.

NCF 2005 Objectives-

Universal (education reaching all without discrimination) lays emphasis on elementary education.

1. The tradition of knowledge work craft is also included in the curriculum adoption of environmental peace as a gene style.
2. Development of children's self-esteem, morality, world, creative.
3. NCF-2005-1993 is the base.
 - It talks about education according to the creation of egalitarian, secular, pluralistic society.
 - Emphasis is placed on interactive techniques in teaching.
 - Flexible school calendar and time schedule that includes excursion activities as needed.
 - Emphasis on strengthening the Panchayati Raj system.

First chapter - Perspective under which the following facts are included :-

1. Social Context Knowledge of Education.

Broadening the concept of knowledge.

New areas of knowledge and experience included.

Self-confidence and critical awareness.

Community Participation Curriculum Decisions.

Objective - Democracy, equality, justice, freedom, charity, development of secularism and respect and commitment to human rights.

2. Learning to learn, development of readiness, creative work education. Dimensions of quality - it discusses all aspects of life :-

- Social justice.
- Peace.
- Peace Environmental, protection Education.
- Talking about education in the context of current challenges.

NCF 2005 Document- 5 Guiding Principles - (Learning without load)

1. Linking to life outside school.
2. Freedom from the rote system of reading.
3. Advancement of curriculum in such a way that children have opportunities for all-round development, rather than remaining textbook-centric.
4. To make the examination more flexible than before and to integrate with the classroom activity.
5. Development of children as citizens who have faith in international values (democracy, secularism, equality) of democratic system.

Chapter II - Learning and Knowledge (NCF-2005)

- Child is active and knows and learns on his own and tries new things, makes mistakes by manipulating, corrects himself, learning is an active and social activity.
- Meaning of Child Centered Pedagogy - Link the list of experiences of children with knowledge.
- Sense of learning should be linked to joy and satisfaction in place of discipline, opposition to punishment, emotional security necessary.
- School, home, community, consider the child's language and culture as important everywhere.
- First of all physical development, nutritious food, physical exercise and psychological social need should be met for learning.

Meaning of Cognition - Understanding oneself and the world through actions and language.

- Meaningful learning - Productive process of presenting concrete objects and mental signals and taking changes in them instead of rote learning. close relationship between the ideas of language.
- Support of school system similar to Kothari Commission.
- A child has the ability to learn by nature, meaning emerges from learning, abstract source interpretation and work is important.

- Learning takes place both inside and outside the school. Learning should be linked to the surrounding world. Let the child experience, by listening, by asking, by experimenting, he keeps a proper place in keeping attitude. Learning should not be mechanical, the child flies away.

Direct learning -

- Development stage of adolescent identity, physical changes at this time, education to remove stereotypes, social education should be given.
- Inclusive environment in the classroom.
- Emphasis on the concept of constructivism in learning.
- Importance of interaction in learning to encourage smart guesswork.
- Activity based learning in learning.

Chapter III - Curriculum

- Be such that provide experiences that increase the capacity of discrimination.
- A chance to understand the world through different methods.
- Development of aesthetic sense. Increase sensitivity towards others.
- Organized presentation of knowledge.
- Education of self-reliance science.

NCF 2005 Basic abilities of the child include language, forming and maintaining relationships, and functional abilities.

Physical, skill knowledge.

Practical Knowledge - Being Connected to Life.

Development of arts, crafts, local knowledge, linking customs with school knowledge.

Incorporation of local environment - physical, social and cultural should be included.

All activities from pre-primary level to primary level - Curriculum Importance of language and speed.

Development of critical attitude towards sensitive reality and environment.

Subject based suggestion - Education in the following way in the subject -

At the primary level - mathematical games, puzzles, calculations.

Higher level - number manipulation, algebra.

Teaching through geometry, theory at the secondary level.

Education in the subject of science - examination of the child's everyday experiences, exploration, poverty, ignorance, faith should be removed.

Development in positive outlook of socially deprived sections.

Civics - Change in Politics.

Environmental Education - Environmental Studies in Class 3 to 5.

Social Science, History, Political Science, Economics should be taught in class 6 to 8.

Arts, singing, dance, handicraft, sports, physical education.

Peace Education - Parting away, Social Values, Tolerance.

There should be force-centred education.

Use of three language formula under -

1. mother tongue / home language.

2. Hindi / Sanskrit.

3. foreign / english.

Chapter IV- School Classroom Environment :-

1. Autograph.

2. Flexibility in Time Array / School Planning.

3. Activities to include both able bodied and disabled children.

4. Interaction should be from both sides (teacher and child).

5. Information technology.

6. Community participation.

7. Library - Connecting the child to the school society.

Principles of Curriculum Development -

- Theory of planning.
- Principle of action.
- Creative principle.
- Principle of coordination.

Under this -

1. The curriculum should be according to the age and level of the students.

2. The curriculum should be according to the ability and interest of the students.

3. The curriculum should be according to the environment (relation to life).

4. The curriculum should be comprehensive.

5. Curriculum goals should be set.

6. Curriculum should be flexible.

7. The curriculum should be such that it provides opportunities to the students to learn.

8. The curriculum should be such that it makes all round development of the students.
9. Curriculum based on Nivanta's research.
10. Curriculum based on correlation.
11. The curriculum should be such that it proves helpful in the future of the students.

Chapter V - It has been told about systemic reform :-

1. Uniform gross system.
2. Curriculum Diversity.
3. Curriculum involving NGO's, involving social groups.
4. Teaching training.
5. Evaluation.
 - Formative Assessment Open Book.
 - 30:1, 200 working days.
 - Homework help.
 - Continuous Comprehensive Evaluation.
 - Qualitative Assessment.
 - There should be open book examination which does not have board, 10th, 12th pass, system of fail should be stopped.
 - Common school system.
 - The need to stop corporal punishment, including computer computing.
 - 10th, 12th should be optional.

Importance of course -

Importance of teacher-learner society for the country.

Conclusion:- In the policy of NCERT - A policy of NCF-2005 is also an important policy, which provides a reformative framework for formulating curriculum and teaching practice towards textbooks in school education programs of India.

Reference List:-

1. [www.co.ncert.nic.in/rightside/links/pdf/frame work nf 2005.pdf](http://www.co.ncert.nic.in/rightside/links/pdf/frame%20work%20of%202005.pdf).
2. Aggarwal/c/and/Agarwal, SP (1989) National Policy Education :- Agenda for India.